

Evaluation of kinetic modeling methods for kaolinitic clay dehydroxylation

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Abstract. Modeling the reaction kinetics of kaolinite dehydroxylation is vital for simulating and optimizing industrial clay calcination. However, because dehydroxylation kinetics vary with mineralogical characteristics, a versatile and robust modeling strategy is required. To address this need, the present work reviews historical studies on kaolinite dehydroxylation kinetics and evaluates several kinetic modeling methods using a thermogravimetric dataset collected at multiple heating rates for representative kaolinitic clays. The methods are compared in terms of fitting accuracy and, crucially, the ability of the resultant models to generalize beyond the experimental heating profiles. The assessment reveals clear differences in predictive power among the approaches, underscoring the importance of a systematic modeling procedure. On this basis, we propose an optimized three-stage framework comprising data pre-processing, kinetic modeling, and information-criteria-based model validation. Altogether, the study provides a practical route to obtain reliable dehydroxylation kinetic models for diverse kaolinitic clays, thereby narrowing the gap between lab-scale experimentation and full-scale calcination process simulations.

Keywords: clay calcination; kaolinite dehydroxylation; kinetic modeling; thermogravimetric analysis.